

Transformational and Instructional Leadership Styles to Improve Teacher Performance: Literature Review

Yuni Rahmawati¹, Hasan Hariri², Riswanti Rini³, Sowiyah⁴

¹ Student Master of Education Administration, Universitas Lampung, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia

^{2,3,4} Lecturer of Education Administration, Universitas Lampung, Bandar Lampung, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The importance of transformational and instructional leadership styles of principals is interesting to study. There are several articles on Transformational and Instructional leadership style reviews found. This literature review aims to determine the transformational and instructional leadership styles of school principals to improve teacher performance. Based on the results of the literature review, it was found that there was a significant relationship between the transformational leadership style and the principal's instructional style to improve teacher performance, which was seen from the increase in teacher performance and teacher job satisfaction in schools. The results of the review article show a significant relationship between transformational and instructional leadership styles in improving teacher performance in schools. There is a positive relationship between transformational and instructional leadership styles and can have a positive and significant influence on teacher behavior and teacher job satisfaction. Principal's Transformational and Instructional Leadership is one of the factors that encourage schools to achieve goals actively and efficiently.

KEYWORDS: Leadership Style, Instructional, Principal, Transformational Teacher Performance

INTRODUCTION

Quality education can be formed and implemented because of the role of a leader or principal who guides teachers and staff to provide quality learning. In an effort to improve teacher performance, a leader or principal must pay attention that the level of performance of each teacher is different. Syadam said that there are several factors that affect the achievement or performance of a teacher in carrying out tasks, namely the level of education, work experience, work environment, supporting equipment or facilities, leadership, and the teacher's own motivation [1]. One of the factors that determine the quality of school education is the leadership and performance of human resources. Teachers as an important resource in schools will determine the achievement of learning objectives. Therefore, teacher performance can be the key to successful management of education in schools. Leadership in an organization can increase satisfaction and have a positive effect on the performance of subordinates [2].

Efforts to improve teacher performance will never succeed optimally without the role of a quality principal's leadership style. The principal's transformational and instructional style is one of the leadership styles that is able to carry out efforts to improve teacher performance. Triyono (2019) states that a leader or principal who applies this transformational leadership style will influence his subordinates with the skills they have to approach mentally and provide guidance or empowerment and mental reinforcement [3]. With the development of the times, this leadership style is considered quite effective as an effort to support teacher performance improvement. This transformational leadership style is a leadership style used by school principals to improve the quality of the schools they lead by changing forms (strategies, learning methods, problem solving, etc.) into different forms in different ways for the better. While the instructional leadership style is a comprehensive style and has high potential in motivating teachers with an emphasis on monitoring students [4]. From this theoretical statement, the author makes the basis that to improve teacher performance a leader or principal can apply transformational and instructional leadership styles.

Teacher performance can be referred to as the ability to perform tasks as a teacher within a certain period of time in a school in order to achieve it [5]. In their efforts, teachers are expected to have good performance, so an evaluation is needed to be able to see the development of teacher performance from year to year. Performance appraisal is an important task for leaders in a school.

Assessing teacher performance in schools is not a simple matter, there needs to be a good communication within the school itself to make a good standard of choice. As an important part in the implementation of the educational process, teachers are required to

have sufficient skills and abilities. Therefore, there are efforts to improve teacher performance. There are two important strategies that can be done to improve teacher performance, namely: training and work motivation. Training is used to deal with the low ability of teachers. While work motivation is used to deal with low morale. Teachers who have good performance are shown by the fulfillment of work targets, quality of work, timeliness and adherence to principles.

Performance is an important aspect in an organization, educational organizations are no exception. The principal is a functional teacher who is given the task of leading a school as a place for the teaching and learning process to take place or a place for interaction between teachers who give lessons and students who receive lessons. In other words, a teacher is given an additional task as a principal to carry out the school leadership function. Thus the principal is a school manager. Principals play an active role in coordinating the improvement of the quality of education in schools. Principals have an important role in improving the quality of school education. The principal as the driving force for improving teacher performance is required to have a broad vision, mission, and insight as well as adequate professional abilities in planning, organizing, implementing and supervising the implementation of education. In addition, school principals are required to have the ability to build harmonious cooperation with various parties related to educational programs in schools. The ability of the principal will certainly affect the performance of teachers in carrying out their duties. One of the principal performance indicators is assessed based on the implementation of their duties and roles. One of the principal roles that is very important is as an administrator and supervisor in an effort to improve teacher performance. The principal's leadership style has an important role in improving teacher performance. There is a positive relationship between transformational leadership style and a significant positive effect on teacher behavior, job satisfaction [6]. Transformational leadership and job satisfaction have a significant positive effect on teacher performance, either directly or indirectly through mediating organizational citizenship behavior [7]. Other researchers suggest that the principal's transformational leadership style looks innovative, committed, and communicative and appreciates achievement, is able to create a conducive atmosphere by making efforts to change awareness, inspire teachers and staff to work together into good team-work. The principal's instructional leadership, namely, providing assistance for teachers starting from planning learning, to evaluating learning. Where, these activities are the main teaching tasks that must be mastered by the teacher. Principals' instructional leadership and teacher performance levels are high and there is a significant relationship between principals' instructional leadership practices and teacher performance. There is a positive and indirect effect related to job satisfaction [8].

Previous studies generally only explained two variables, not all variables were reviewed together. For this reason, this study was conducted to analyze the effect of the principal's transformational and instructional leadership styles to improve teacher performance. This research is expected to be an input for policy makers regarding the influence of the transformational leadership style and the principal's instructional style to improve teacher performance.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Principal Leadership

Leadership is a skill or ability of an individual possessed by a leader in influencing and directing people who are in the same group to achieve goals. Kippen Berger states that leadership is a fact of the process carried out by a leader to convince the people around him to have the motivation and initiative in working together as a form of effort to achieve mutually agreed goals [9]. According to the Ministry of National Education, the principal has a leadership component, namely (1) having a strong personality. (2) understand the conditions of teachers, employees and students well. (3) have a vision and understand the school's mission. (4) decision-making ability and (5) communication skills. The principal's leadership ability is the main determinant of teacher empowerment and improvement of learning processes and products [10]. The principal is the person most responsible for the performance of teachers and employees in the school [11]. operationally the principal's leadership is the leader's ability to lead an education in influencing and motivating employees to achieve school goals. The indicators are (1) decision making, (2) work distribution, (3) delegation of authority, (4) monitoring and evaluation, and (5) implementation of Specific Instructional objectives [10]. According to [12] there are several components that allow the principal to exert influence in his leadership, namely: a) authority, namely the formal right to make decisions; b) power, namely the ability to give rewards or punishments; and c) influence, namely the ability to have decisions to be implemented without being associated with authority and power. The principal has an important role in influencing; push; guide; direct; and mobilize teachers, staff, students, parents, and other stakeholders to achieve the goals that have been set

[13]. The significant influence of school leadership on all elements of the school, has a positive effect on the quality of teaching and learning. The function of leadership is to design organizational conditions that foster high quality in teaching and result in improved learning outcomes.

Transformational Leadership Style

Wawat Hermawati stated that transformational leadership is described as leadership that arouses or motivates subordinates to be able to develop and achieve higher performance or levels so that they are able to achieve more than they previously expected (beyond expectations). Transformational leaders are able to generate and provide motivation for the goals to be achieved together [14]. Rafudin stated that the Transformational Leadership Style is a way to influence other people so that they are willing to follow by exploring the human potential of the people who are influenced [15]. Meanwhile, according to Newstrom and Bass (in Sadeghi & Pihie, 2012) transformational leaders have certain characteristics, including being trustworthy and fair, having clear goals, having high expectations, providing support and appreciation, encouraging them, and directing followers to see things. more can be accomplished than they think Transformational leaders have certain characteristics, including being trustworthy and fair, having clear goals, having high expectations, providing support and appreciation, encouraging them, and directing followers to see things that are good for them can achieve more than what they achieve think about .

Based on some of the opinions above, it can be concluded that transformational leadership is a leader who is able to provide motivation or encouragement , and also provides direction to his subordinates to be able to achieve goals together. Transformational leaders must also have the ability to match the vision of the future with their subordinates, as well as raise the needs of subordinates at a higher level than they need.

There are four identified transformational leadership, [16]. 1) school leaders provide role models in school attendance and care for their members, especially low performers; 2) as a school administrator must have a strategy in solving existing problems; 3) as an inspiration for the school community and 4) being a role model for all school members.

Instructional Leadership Style

Instructional Leadership Style is a way to influence other people so that they want to follow by exploring the human potential of the people who are influenced [15]. Hallingers & Murphy (1985) stated that effective instructional leadership is as follows: (1) the meaning of the school's vision through various opinions with school members and as well as striving for the school's vision and mission to thrive in its implementation, (2) principals involve stakeholders in the management of education, (3) the principal provides support for learning, (4) the principal monitors the teaching and learning process to understand more deeply and realize what is going on in the school, (5) the principal acts as a facilitator so that with various how he can find out learning difficulties and can help teachers in overcoming these learning difficulties [15]. Instructional leadership focuses on teaching and learning and on the behavior of teachers in working with students. The leader's influence is targeted at student learning through the teacher [18]. Principal's instructional leadership is the behavior of principals who prioritize their activities on learning, namely by influencing, directing, and guiding teachers in teaching and learning activities so that teachers can provide the best learning services to students [16]. "It seems that instructional leadership is nothing more than a shorthand way of describing the influence and practice of leadership in organizations that has an impact on student achievement. The three domains of instructional leadership are: defining the school's mission, creating a positive learning climate, and overseeing the school's teaching program" [20].

Teacher Performance

Regarding performance, Supardi argues that performance is the result of work that has been achieved by someone in an organization to achieve goals based on standardization or size and time that is adjusted to the type of work and in accordance with established norms and ethics [19]. The statement indicates that performance as a process and the final result of an activity carried out by an employee in achieving organizational goals must be based on predetermined standards or measures. Teacher performance is the ability and success of teachers in carrying out learning tasks. Teacher performance can also be influenced by various factors, one of the factors that influence performance is the principal's leadership [14]. The performance of a teacher is very important in educating students and for the future of the nation. It should be noted that the duties of a teacher have been regulated in the RI Law No. 14 of 2005, namely "teachers are professional educators with the main tasks of educating, guiding, teaching, directing, training, assessing and evaluating students at the level of early childhood education, education and training. primary, and secondary education [21].

There are many environmental factors that can affect teacher performance, three of which are as follows: 1. Principal Leadership
Principal leadership is the effort of an individual who is trusted as an organizational leader in a school that influences its members including teachers, staff/employees, students, and school committee to realize an educational goal. 2. Principal's Motivation.
Principal's motivation is an encouragement given by principals to teachers to be more active in carrying out teacher performance which includes planning, implementing, and evaluating. 3. A conducive climate
Good classroom management, ability to manage facilities and good infrastructure, as well as relationships between teachers, students, employees, and principals that can create a pleasant school atmosphere. This can create feelings of pleasure and enthusiasm for teachers who are carrying out their duties [22].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research is a literature study. The purpose of this literature review is to obtain a theoretical basis that can support in solving a problem. The author conducts this literature study after determining the topic of writing and determining the formulation of the problem, before going into the field to collect the necessary data. The review process begins with a search on a search engine; Google Scholar, for articles containing these keywords; "leadership, principals, efforts to improve teacher performance". The search ranges from articles published between 2003-2022, Articles related to the mentioned keywords. The inclusion criteria in this study were:

- a. Qualitative and quantitative results "Transformational leadership, and Instructional, Teacher performance improvement."
 - b. Research from various countries in the world
 - c. Research articles are written in English and Indonesian
 - d. Dissertations and theses are excluded
- The steps in this literature review are:

Step 1: Define the problem

- Choose a topic that is relevant to your problem and interest
- Problems must be written completely and accurately

Step 2: Search literature

- Search literature relevant to the research
- Get an overview of the research topic
- Research sources will be comfortable if they are supported by knowledge related to the topic being studied.
- Sources must provide an overview/summary related to previous research.

Step 3: Evaluation data

- Attend to contributions made by articles on the topic
- Attend to contribute articles related to the topic
- Data can be quantitative data, qualitative data, or a combination of both.

Step 4: Analysis and interpretation.

- Discuss and summarize the literature.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The following presents the results of a literature study that the author has done. The results obtained focus on transformational and instructional leadership on teachers. The articles reviewed are research conducted in several countries in the world. The scope of this research was carried out in several schools and universities. The results of the literature review that the author has done are shown in the table below:

Title	Author and Year	Country	Method	Result
The Influence of Teachers' Self-Efficacy and School Leaders' Transformational Leadership Practices on Teachers' Innovative Behavior	MA Zainal and MEE MohdMatore (2021)	Malaysia	Quantitative	The results of the study suggest that teacher self efficacy and school administrators' transformational leadership practices both play a role in influencing innovative behavior of teachers.
Effective Instructional Leadership can Enhance Teachers' Motivation and Improve Students' Learning Outcomes	Dr. Farah Naz and Surryia Rashid(2021)	Lahore	Quantitative	The results showed that leaders encourage teamwork to develop positive relationships between parents and school staff. They agreed that principals are trying to change the school climate according to new trends.
The Moderation Role of Transformational Leadership in the Effect of Instructional Leadership on Teacher Professional Learning and Instructional Practice: An Integrated Leadership Perspective	M.. Bellibaş, A. Kılınç, and M.Polatcan (2021)	Turkey	Quantitative	The results of the study suggest that the influence of instructional leadership and transformational leadership practices can maximize their effect on students achievement through teacher learning, and better address evolving problems demands for educational reform.
Principal's Instructional Leadership in Improving Teacher Performance	SLH Rida Aulia Putri (2022)	Indonesia	Qualitative	The results of this study illustrate that instructional leadership can influence teacher teaching performance
The influence of transformational leadership Principal on teacher performance	L. Akbar and N. Imaniyati, (2019)	Indonesia	Quantitative	The results showed that there was a positive and significant effect of transformational leadership on teacher performance.
The effect of instructional, transformational and spiritual leadership on elementary school teachers' performance and students' achievements	A. Nurabadi, J. Irianto, I. Bafadal, Juharyanto, I. Gunawan, and MA Adha, (2021)	Indonesia	Quantitative	he findings show that: (1) there is a direct effect of instructional leadership on teachers' performance, transformational leadership on teachers' performance, spiritual leadership on teachers' performance, instructional leadership on students' achievement, transformational leadership on students' achievement, spiritual leadership on students' achievement, and teachers' performance on students' achievements. In addition, (2) there is an indirect effect of instructional leadership on students' achievement through teachers' performance,

				transformational leadership on students' achievement through teachers' performance and spiritual leadership on students' achievement through teachers' performance
Kindergarten principal's transformational leadership contribution and Influence of principal's instructional leadership and climate school on school effectiveness	Agustin, SDNK (2018)	Indonesia	Quantitative	The results of the study show that the picture of leadership principal's instructional, school climate, and school effectiveness in the very high category, Leadership instructional and school climate have a significant and significant effect on school effectiveness.
The influence of instructional leadership on Teacher teaching performance in primary schools	T. Fatonah and J. (2022)	Indonesia	Quantitative	that instructional leadership has a significant positive effect on the teaching performance of teachers in primary schools.
Transformational leadership school principles to teach performance and school quality	A. Rahmi, I. Bafadal, A. Imron, and S. Utaya (2022)	Indonesia	Quantitative	The results showed (1) there is a direct relationship the relationship between the principal's transformational leadership and teacher performance at SMAN Banjarmasin Kota, (2) there is a direct influence relationship between school organizational climate and performance teacher at SMAN Banjarmasin, (3) there is a direct relationship between teacher professional attitude and teacher performance in Banjarmasin City Senior High School, (4) there is an indirect relationship between Principal transformational leadership and performance teachers because of the organizational climate at SMAN Banjarmasin and (5) there is an indirect relationship between transformational principal's leadership and teacher performance because professional attitude of high school teachers in Banjarmasin

This article discusses the practice of Transformational and Instructional leadership on teachers from various schools in various countries. The table above shows that research studies on Transformational and Instructional Leadership have been conducted in schools and universities. Based on the results of a literature review and a review of the sources obtained, the analysis shows that transformational and instructional leadership styles play an important role in improving teacher performance in schools. There is a positive relationship between transformational and instructional leadership styles and can have a positive and significant influence on teacher behavior and teacher job satisfaction. So the level of achievement of teacher performance cannot be separated from the

influence of the Transformational and Instructional leadership styles of the principal. Principal's Transformational and Instructional Leadership is one of the factors that encourage schools to achieve goals actively and efficiently. The role of the principal as an educational leader is required to carry out his duties and responsibilities as well as possible regarding his leadership as a principal, including as a teaching leader. The principal's transformational and instructional leadership style makes the school a school that has the power to grow and develop into a superior school.

CONCLUSION

The principal's leadership style plays an important role in improving teacher performance, every increase in the quality of the principal's leadership style, the teacher's performance will also increase. because the principal's leadership style can create positive and significant changes in education by encouraging teachers or their subordinates to take initiative and change. The results of this literature review show that the principal's leadership style is very important for educational institutions. Transformational and Instructional leadership style is a leadership style that is able to provide a motivation and also an encouragement to influence others so that they are willing to follow by exploring the potential possessed by the teacher or his subordinates.

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Cite this Article: Yuni Rahmawati, Hasan Hariri, Riswanti Rini, Sowiyah (2022). Transformational and Instructional Leadership Styles to Improve Teacher Performance: Literature Review. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 5(7), 2757-2764